

Smarandache's new geometries a provocation for an ammelioration of human condition

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ABSTRACT

Are remarked the new Geometries of Smarandache and it is given a relationship and an application of Smarandache Paradoxist Geometry to the ammelioration of human condition by a better understanding of ourselves and of others.

Key words: Non-euclidean Geometry, Bolyai/Lobacewski/Gauss and Riemann Geometry, Smarandache Paradoxist Geometry

In [2], [3], Florentin Smarandache introduced a new type of Geometry. In this Smarandacheian space it is proposed to be considered the theory deduced from the Absolute Geometry of Bolyai and Lobacewski in which the axiom of parallel it is accepted for some pairs of points and lines and it is denied for others. This new Geometry generalizes and unites in the same time: Euclid, Bolyai/Lobacewski/Gauss and Riemann Geometries.

If the first Non-euclidean Geometry introduced by Lobacewski, Bolyai and Gauss surprised the world, such that Gauss said that the people were not prepared to receive a new theory, now we know and accept many kinds of new Geometries. Even in 1969 Florentin Smarandache had put the problem to study a new Geometry in which the parallel from a point to a line to be unique only for some pairs of points and lines and for others: none or more, even infinitely many parallels could be drawn through some points to a line.

Are nowadays people surprise for such new ideas and new Geometries? Certainly not! After then the formalized theories were introduced in Mathematics, a lot of new Geometries could be accepted and semantically to be proved to be non-contradictory by the models created for them as in [1].

In [4] we introduced a new notion for understanding the great diversity of human condition, that of "inner Geometry". Conformly with this notion we differ so much after

the degree of manifestation of our inner possibilities, and from here, after our own blockade of them. To be able to understand and to improve our interhuman relationships these new types of Geometries could help in at least two directions. For a hand, we are in different type of "inner Geometry" from a moment to another moment, and for the other hand: from a person to other one, this "inner Geometry" could be different. In this acceptation we can treat each other with more wisdom, we can find an explanation of so exposed human condition, to be more conscious about the greatness of self knowledge and to imply more in the ammelioration of the existence as a theory in which we want to be with more concilliation. Smarandache's Geometries could be considered in this way, as an important reflection about human condition and his Paradoxist Geometry to find a new model in the theory of existence.

References

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